

A system for independent evaluation of clinical prediction models while preserving intellectual property and data privacy

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Abstract

Evaluating clinical prediction models (CPMs) in new patients and settings is essential for building the evidence needed to support their adoption in practice. Independent evaluation by researchers distinct from the CPM developers is particularly valued, yet remains underutilised due to barriers of data access, governance, and technical complexity. Here we propose a novel two-component system enabling any researcher to conduct a fully independent evaluation of a static CPM, with no requirement to share patient data, no specialist infrastructure, and minimal code. The system lowers the barrier to evaluation while providing developers with confidence that CPMs are evaluated exactly as intended. The system also resolves a growing tension between open science and commercial viability: model parameters remain under the developer’s control and are protected throughout, preserving intellectual property while enabling evaluation to proceed. We introduce **evaluatr**, a free R package that implements the workflow. The proposed system provides a viable pathway toward widespread evaluation and ultimately impact for promising CPMs, where few routes currently exist.

1. Introduction

Clinical prediction models (CPMs) have the potential to enhance decision-making in healthcare, leading to improved patient and resource outcomes [1, 2]. Despite vast hype and investment in such CPMs, evidence of performance and of widespread impact on improving healthcare outcomes remains scarce [3, 4]. Among myriad reasons behind CPMs not progressing to implementation and impact, one evolving issue is the conflict between open science and commercialisation [5].

1.1 *The open science imperative*

Open science is a core principle of research, promoting transparency, reproducibility, accessibility and impact of research. In the field of CPMs such principles are embedded in the TRI-POD+AI reporting guidelines, which encourage transparency and reproducibility – including full reporting of the CPM specification (e.g. model coefficients for regression-based tools) [6, 7]. The primary reasons for this are to facilitate fully independent CPM evaluation, and reproducibility of the CPM for use in practice. External evaluation studies assess the performance of a CPM in new patients and settings

that differ from that in which the CPM was originally developed. These studies are of utmost importance for CPMs to demonstrate generalisability toward wider adoption [8]. Performance of a CPM in new settings is often heterogeneous, and understanding this heterogeneity (through widespread evaluations) is key to understanding the expected performance if the CPM is widely adopted. Independent evaluation [9], in which the evaluation is undertaken by authors distinct from those involved in the CPM's derivation, is critical to avoid potential spin and over-optimism [10–12]. While the principles of open science are essential for scientific integrity and transparency, they are also incompatible with the existing industry-centric landscape of regulatory governance.

1.2 The commercial reality

Unlike other areas of healthcare such as pharmaceutical interventions or diagnostic tests, many CPMs historically originate in academia, not industry. As such, many are publicly or charitably funded through time-limited grants, rather than commercial entities. This finite funding source creates barriers once a CPM reaches the point of potential implementation into routine practice. Over the last decade, most global healthcare regulators have started implementing increasingly rigorous frameworks that define most CPMs as medical devices, necessitating a range of resource and time-consuming legal and infrastructural obligations before they can be implemented. The aim is principled – patients rightly expect safety and efficacy. However, meeting and maintaining regulatory certification necessitates substantial pre-market and ongoing post-market investment for the lifetime that the device is intended for clinical use [13]. For example, in Great Britain, for a CPM which is intended to allow direct diagnosis or monitoring of vital physiological processes, initial costs can be up to £200,000 if document review by a

notified approval body is required, with ongoing annual costs in the region of £6,000–£40,000, with additional costs related to indemnity and liability insurance [14, 15]. These figures do not capture the ongoing personnel burden of maintaining regulatory compliance, including managing complaints, software updates, bug reports, and post-market surveillance requirements. Without a clear plan to enable self-sustainability, the current landscape is financially unviable and thus prohibitive for real-world impact for most developers. Furthermore, should developers make the CPM specification freely available, intellectual property is difficult to protect and the potential for commercialisation to improve viability weakens. This begs the question of how the continuing costs to enable clinical impact will be funded to ensure that public benefit is realised from the vast number of publicly funded CPMs. Recent updates to reporting guidelines have broadened the scope for model reporting to include the reporting of “formula, code, model objects or application programming interfaces that allow predictions in new individuals and to enable third party evaluation and implementation” – creating an important opportunity for viable solutions to this issue [6].

1.3 The methodological gap

There are currently no public funding sources available to support the continued costs of maintaining regulatory certification, and no public entity offering support to host or fund a CPM post-market for its lifetime. This forces developers to choose between open science (transparency) and the potential for impact of the CPM in practice (viability).

Existing solutions require a sacrifice on one side of the scale. One could forgo transparency using obfuscation of the CPM to protect intellectual property, allowing for the CPM to be implemented within a commercially available appli-

cation (e.g. web calculator, mobile or desktop app). One such example is the FRAX tool, a CPM for prediction of an individual’s 10-year probability of osteoporotic fracture, available through a paid app [16, 17]. The underlying CPMs have never been fully published, obstructing any independent evaluation of the CPM. Alternatively, one could follow a fully transparent approach, reporting the underlying CPM at the cost of viability. Where the full model specification is freely available, commercial entities have little incentive to assume the considerable regulatory obligations of a registered manufacturer, because any competitor could market an identical product at lower cost. As a result, many promising CPMs with strong and growing evidence bases remain confined to the pages of academic journals rather than clinical practice, because no viable route to regulatory approval exists [3].

No system currently exists that satisfies both scientific transparency and commercial viability. Here we propose one potential solution.

2. System Conceptualisation

2.1 *The system architecture*

Our proposal consists of a two-component system: a developer-side (secure repository) and an evaluator-side (software package). The developer-side consists of a CPM specification file (e.g. model structure, transformation of variables etc.) stored in a secure GitHub repository. On the evaluator-side we have developed an R

package (**evaluatr**) to retrieve CPM specifications and compute the predicted probability of outcome for each individual in an evaluation dataset (see Figure 1).

The workflow is straightforward. The developer uses a utility function in **evaluatr** to write a specification file containing metadata related to their developed CPM, which may include information on the type of model, the variables included in the CPM, the parameter values (e.g. regression coefficients) associated with each variable, the baseline hazard or intercept, etc. The **evaluatr** package contains built-in prediction logic for supported CPM structures; the specification file supplies the parameter values that this logic requires. The developer uploads these specifications to a private repository, thereby preserving intellectual property.

The evaluator contacts the developer with their intention to evaluate the CPM in their dataset/setting, and the developer provides an access token and the address of the private repository. The evaluator uses these two pieces of information to authenticate themselves through the **evaluatr** package. Once authenticated, the package retrieves the CPM specification file and applies the appropriate built-in prediction method to compute predictions locally without revealing the CPM specification on the evaluator-side. Predictions are computed locally on the evaluator-side, preserving data privacy and facilitating the calculation of any CPM performance metric of interest [18].

Figure 1. Evaluation system structural diagram. The developer provides protected algorithm metadata, undisclosed to the evaluator, while enabling independent evaluation without data transfer to the developer. Outputs returned to the evaluator enable flexible performance evaluation but are protected against clinical use.

2.2 Core principles

There are four core principles at the heart of our proposed system.

Evaluator-side autonomy

Evaluator-side autonomy ensures that researchers (evaluators) external to the CPM derivation team (developers) have complete control over the data used to evaluate the CPM and the reporting of results of the evaluation. This autonomy satisfies the requirements of independent CPM evaluation [9, 19], avoiding the potential biases of non-independent evaluations [10]. Furthermore, the evaluators’ autonomy over the data means the system removes barriers to data access for evaluation, in an approach akin to federated data analysis, where the CPM can be applied to the data *in situ* with only a basic familiarity with R, after which performance metrics can be returned to the evaluator [20, 21].

Developer-side oversight/IP protection

Developer-side oversight provides two benefits. Firstly, the CPM developer maintains the spec-

ification (the parameter values, variable definitions, and any required pre-processing) that ensures the CPM is evaluated exactly as intended [22]. Existing evaluation studies commonly fail to apply the published CPM as specified – for example, where the CPM was developed using a Cox proportional hazards model, often the evaluator will omit the baseline survival from their calculations for individual predictions [22]. Developers using the proposed system can be assured the CPM is correctly implemented. Secondly, the developer retains the intellectual property related to the CPM securely in a remote, private repository. This principle therefore enables the opportunity for the developer to commercialise the CPM, if necessary, to support the funding of regulatory and implementation costs as the CPM progresses through the translational pipeline sustainably.

Data privacy & scientific transparency

As a result of the first two principles, the scientific transparency and data privacy principles hold. Scientific transparency is upheld by allowing full evaluation capabilities to the independent evaluator, whilst not compromising on

methodological rigour in how the CPM is applied to compute individual predictions. Data privacy is upheld by ensuring that patient data never leaves the evaluator’s secure environment. The evaluator retains control over compliance with the relevant region-specific standards (e.g. GDPR, EHDS, HIPAA etc.) for handling pa-

tient data safely and securely.

The system enables several benefits addressing the concerns of all stakeholders invested in CPMs. Table 1 gives an overview of key requirements in the process, how these are addressed by the system, and which stakeholders benefit.

Table 1. Requirements addressed by the **evaluatr** system.

Requirement	How the system addresses it	Stakeholders who benefit
Independent, unbiased evaluation	Evaluator has full autonomy over data and reporting; developer cannot influence results	Evaluators, patients, regulators, journals
CPM applied as intended	Developer specifies prediction logic centrally; evaluatr executes it verbatim, removing common misapplication errors (e.g. omitted baseline survival)	Developers, evaluators, patients
Data sovereignty and patient privacy	Evaluation data never leaves the evaluator’s local environment; no patient information is transmitted to any third party	Evaluators, patients, healthcare systems, regulators (GDPR/HIPAA)
Protection of intellectual property	Model specification is stored securely on the developer-side and never disclosed to the evaluator in usable form	Developers
Prevention of misuse as a clinical tool	Output is a permuted prediction–outcome matrix; individual predictions cannot be linked back to patient variables; a minimum dataset size is enforced	Patients, regulators, developers
Audit trail and accountability	Every evaluation event is logged; developers can monitor who has evaluated their model and when	Developers, regulators
Lowering the barrier to evaluation	Minimal code, no data-sharing agreements, no specialist infrastructure required	Evaluators, patients, healthcare systems

3. Implementation Considerations

Having established the conceptual system, we now address its practical implementation.

3.1 Technical requirements

The **evaluatr** system is designed for accessibility, requiring minimal technical infrastructure from either party, facilitating easy adoption. Beyond the dataset on which they wish to eval-

uate the CPM, the evaluator requires access to the free R software environment, the internet, and an authentication token provided by the CPM developer. A minimal working knowledge of the R software environment is needed for either party to use the **evaluatr** system. On the developer-side a private (or public) GitHub repository is required to deploy the CPM for future evaluation through the system. To sup-

port developers in preparing their CPM for the system, **evaluatr** also provides a utility function that accepts a fitted R model object and produces a correctly formatted, ready-to-deploy specification file. This reduces the developer-side setup and evaluator-side implementation

to a small number of R commands. Box 1 illustrates the complete evaluator-side workflow, demonstrating the minimal code required to compute predictions and derive performance metrics in a new dataset.

Complete evaluator workflow: three steps from dataset to performance metrics
Requires R, the `evaluatr` package, and the four identifiers provided by the model developer

- 1 Install the package**
Install `evaluatr` and load it into the R session. The access token provided by the developer should be stored and handled in accordance with local institutional data security practices.

```
install.packages("evaluatr")
library("evaluatr")
```
- 2 Compute predictions**
Pass the local dataset and the four developer-supplied identifiers to `secure_model_validation()`. Model specifications are retrieved and used to compute predictions. Patient data never leaves the local environment.

```
result <- secure_model_validation(
  repo_owner = "developer-github-username",
  repo_name = "model-repository-name",
  model_id = "model_v1",
  github_token = <token provided by developer>,
  data = my_dataset,
  outcome = "outcome_column"
)
```

Patient data stays local
Coefficients not exposed
Predictions shuffled on return
- 3 Compute performance metrics**
Pass the result object to `eval_performance()`. The evaluator has complete autonomy over this step - any threshold, any subgroup, any metric of interest. Evaluators can compute metrics separately.

```
performance <- eval_performance(
  validation_result = result,
  generate_plots = TRUE,
  confidence_intervals = TRUE,
  n_boot = 1000,
  decision_threshold = 0.15, # clinically defined
  by = my_dataset$subgroup # optional
)
```

Output: discrimination (AUROC), calibration (intercept,slope, ICI, O:E ratio), overall performance (Brier score, R²), clinical utility (net benefit), with 95% CIs and optional diagnostic plots – all computed locally.

Full evaluator autonomy
Subgroup analysis supported
No developer access to results

The shuffled prediction–outcome matrix returned in Step 2 means predictions cannot be matched back to individual patient records, preventing reverse-engineering of the clinical prediction model and precluding use for individual-level clinical decisions.

Box 1. The evaluator-side workflow: three steps from dataset to performance metrics.

The **evaluatr** package currently supports CPMs derived using logistic regression, Cox proportional hazards, Weibull accelerated failure time, and multinomial logistic regression structures, covering the large majority of regression-based CPMs encountered in practice. For

each supported type, the prediction method is implemented within the package itself; developers supply only the parameter values specific to their CPM. Where a CPM requires pre-processing of the evaluation dataset before predictions are computed (for example, log-

transforming a predictor or deriving an interaction term), developers can specify this as a short code string in the specification file, which the package executes locally in the evaluator’s environment. The two-component architecture is designed to accommodate additional model types in future versions of the package.

One technical consideration in any evaluation study is the handling of missing data in the evaluation dataset. It is advisable to address missingness prior to the computation of predictions [8]. Many approaches exist for handling missingness, and we do not cover these here. Evaluators are free to employ whichever missing data approach they deem most suitable prior to using the system to compute predictions. Alternatively, developers could incorporate missing data handling within their specification file pre-processing. In the future, the **evaluatr** package could look to include built-in imputation options to further facilitate widespread evaluations.

3.2 Security architecture

The system incorporates multiple layers of protection for model coefficients. Prior to storage, coefficient values are transformed and encrypted such that even unintended exposure of the repository would not yield a usable model specification. Access is controlled through unique, time-limited tokens issued by the developer to each evaluator individually, revocable at any time. Every evaluation run is logged by the system, providing the developer with a record of all use. Once the specification reaches the evaluator’s machine, predictions are computed within a compiled layer of the package; coefficient values are not accessible as readable objects in the user’s R session in the ordinary course of use. Responsibility for vetting evaluators rests with the developer, who is encouraged to verify institutional affiliation and satisfy themselves that no conflict of interest exists prior to issu-

ing a token. This gatekeeper role mirrors the governance expectations that apply to any responsible sharing of proprietary scientific work.

3.3 Outputs of the system

At its core it is only necessary for the system to provide evaluators with a set of predicted probabilities for all individuals in the evaluation dataset, as the combination of predictions with outcomes allows computation of any potential performance metric of interest. However, providing CPM predictions alone presents two potential problems for the system and so requires a novel solution. Firstly, it may be possible to reverse-engineer the CPM specification given information on an individual’s values of all variables included in the CPM in combination with their predicted probabilities [9], thus failing the goal of IP protection (viability). Secondly, if it were possible to obtain predictions for a single individual using the system, it could conceivably be misused to implement the CPM in practice and ultimately to misuse the CPM predictions to guide care for an individual patient. The **evaluatr** package itself could then fall under the remit of healthcare regulators and be subject to certification as a medical device. It is not our intention for this system to be used as a method to implement a CPM in practice.

To address these concerns, the package returns only a row-permuted matrix ($N \times 2$) of paired predictions and outcomes, in which each prediction has been decoupled from its corresponding patient’s variable values in the evaluation dataset. This design means that even with full knowledge of a patient’s predictor values, the matching prediction cannot be identified, preventing reverse-engineering of model parameters. To prevent the second issue, we propose a minimum evaluation dataset size ($n = 50$) for use with the package (applied per subgroup when subgroup-level performance is requested), reinforcing that the package cannot be applied

for single-patient use. This hard minimum data size, in combination with the rate limit on key fetch requests, also prevents systematic linear algebra reverse-engineering of the CPM specification. We also caution that this minimum dataset size is far below that recommended by current guidelines on sample size requirements for evaluation studies [23]. These solutions prevent both issues raised above while still allowing the evaluator to compute any performance metric of interest for their evaluation dataset.

Beyond the core output of **evaluatr** we also provide functions to compute a set of standard performance metrics (discrimination, calibration, and clinical utility measures) as recommended in the wider literature for some common outcome types, with additional metrics being added over time [18]. Further, we also provide functions to produce common visualisations used to assess CPM performance at evaluation (e.g. calibration plots, distribution plots, decision curves). The inclusion of these functions serves to facilitate the ease of evaluation and encourage widespread evaluations.

One common evaluation question is to assess the performance of a CPM in particular subgroups of individuals (e.g. ethnicities) or settings (e.g. countries). To facilitate this, the package also allows evaluators to specify a subgroup variable within **evaluatr**. When this option is specified, the permuted prediction–outcome matrix also includes this subgrouping variable to maintain the relationship between the prediction, outcome, and individual’s value of the subgrouping variable. This enables calculation of performance metrics within levels of the subgroup variable (in this case the minimum dataset size applies to each subgroup). This option can also be used to compute performance metrics across multiply imputed datasets by setting the subgroup variable as the imputation dataset identifier.

4. Resolving a Transparency Dilemma

TRIPOD reporting guidelines have historically encouraged authors to present the full prediction model specification, enabling any reader to apply the model independently (item 15a/b, Collins et al. 2015 [7]). For regression-based CPMs, this means publishing all coefficient estimates, therefore foreclosing commercialisation. The recently updated TRIPOD+AI guidelines [6] revise this requirement and now encourage developers to:

“Provide details of the full prediction model (e.g. formula, code, object, application programming interface) to allow predictions in new individuals and to enable third party evaluation and implementation, including any restrictions to access or reuse.”

This revision, driven in part by recognition that complex models cannot always be captured in a simple formula, creates explicit space for software-mediated access in place of coefficient disclosure. Our system is directly compatible with this item: the **evaluatr** package constitutes the “application programming interface” through which third-party evaluations are enabled. The key claim of TRIPOD, that reporting must be sufficient to allow independent evaluation, is fully preserved; what changes is the mechanism.

We encourage journals that enforce TRIPOD+AI standards to accept manuscripts that adopt this system in place of direct coefficient reporting, provided that evaluators, reviewers, or editors can confirm independent access to compute predictions via the package.

5. Broader Implications and Future Directions

Beyond resolving immediate conflicts, this system has broader implications for how CPM

research evolves.

5.1 *Changing the landscape*

Our proposed system creates a sustainable route for the translation of CPMs to generate diverse evidence bases, paving the way both for effective independent evaluation and self-sustainability through IP protection. This combination creates a pathway which increases confidence in the reliability and accuracy of CPMs while simultaneously increasing the probability of promising CPMs reaching clinical implementation and ultimately having the impact they were designed for.

As model performance may severely vary across settings, populations, and time, it is advisable to undertake widespread evaluation studies across myriad settings, including temporally [24]. We believe that a strong route to clinical impact is increased focus on evaluation of a few promising CPMs [5], rather than perpetual development of new CPMs with insufficient evidence. Providing the community with the **evaluatr** package will meaningfully lower the barrier to conducting independent evaluation studies. The evaluator-side workflow requires no specialist technical knowledge beyond basic familiarity with R, and no negotiation of data-sharing agreements or governance approvals beyond what the evaluator already holds for their own dataset. We anticipate this will expand the pool of researchers able to conduct and publish independent evaluations, particularly in settings where resource or governance constraints have historically made such studies impractical.

To support discoverability, the **evaluatr** system maintains a public model registry. When a developer registers a CPM with the system, it is automatically listed in a searchable directory that records the model name, developer contact details, and a plain-language description. Evaluators can query this directory directly from

R using `list_registered_models()`. This removes a further practical barrier: researchers interested in evaluating a CPM no longer need to identify through informal channels whether the system has been adopted for that CPM and who to contact for a token. Developers who wish to keep their model unlisted (e.g. for ongoing regulatory reasons) can opt out at registration.

5.2 *Regulatory and ethical considerations*

The system also enables some benefits in regard to existing regulatory and ethical challenges. The package includes safeguards to ensure appropriate use boundaries, for example by ensuring that patient data never leaves the evaluator’s local environment, thus ensuring data sovereignty compliance. As discussed previously, safeguards have been put in place to obstruct the use of the software as a medical device to inform care for individuals, thus avoiding potential misuse of the software, potential harms for patients, and unnecessary regulation of the software. The ethical and regulatory landscape has evolved in recent years to recognise that CPMs may disadvantage subpopulations by replicating or exacerbating existing biases [25–27]. The system supports computing model performance within subpopulations. In addition, facilitating independent evaluation is empowering and can promote CPM evaluation in populations and settings that are currently underrepresented in research, such as ethnic minorities and low- and middle-income countries.

5.3 *Extension opportunities*

The two-component architecture of the system allows this system to be extended to other CPM structures. One exciting future direction is the extension to CPMs based on unsupervised learning methods that may require processing on the evaluation data, which could be incorporated within our system through a combination of the developer-side specifications (altering inputs to **evaluatr**) and the built-in prediction

logic (altering outputs of **evaluatr**). This kind of information, to enable calculation of such models, is a requirement already specified in the TRIPOD+AI guideline (see earlier) and in regulatory frameworks [6, 28]. Where non-standard pre-processing is required (for example to handle imaging-derived features or complex feature engineering), developers can supply a pre-processing code string alongside their parameter values, which the package executes locally in the evaluator’s environment before applying the built-in prediction logic.

6. Limitations and Considerations

As with any novel concept, the **evaluatr** system has limitations that merit consideration.

6.1 Technical limitations

Practically, the system relies on an API to communicate between the evaluator and developer-side components; this is inherently dependent on the evaluator having access to the internet, which could in unique situations pose an issue. For example, if the evaluator is only able to access the intended evaluation data through a secure remote server which prohibits some functionality on the server to prevent risks, one such restriction may be access to the internet.

6.2 Methodological constraints

Some may argue that only fully reporting the CPM specification allows for a detailed evaluation of the CPM in a new setting, but we argue that the system presented here fulfils the goals of independent evaluation without the need to disclose intellectual property and limit commercialisation potential. The aims of fully independent evaluation of a CPM are to produce a true and fair view of the performance of the CPM in the new setting, an aim fully addressed by the **evaluatr** tool. It could also be argued that the potential for CPM updating will be limited without the full CPM specification. However, the most commonly occurring

update approaches are possible using the system’s output [29, 30]. Updating of the baseline (e.g. model intercept), or scaling of the linear predictor such as uniform shrinkage, Platt scaling, or isotonic regression, can be undertaken using the prediction–outcome matrix output from the **evaluatr** tool. Only the most extreme updating approaches would be incompatible with this system (i.e. re-estimating all or specific variable weights individually, or adding new variables to the existing CPM) due to the decoupling of the prediction–outcome matrix from the variable values. Though such methods could be considered a new model development [22].

6.3 Community adoption

It is our hope that the system is adopted widely to provide a new pathway to improved evidence generation for CPMs and ultimately a route to impact. Potential barriers to the adoption of the system include the initial investment of time and effort for developers in learning how to prepare and set up the developer-side documentation. In practice there is likely to be a very small learning curve for developers, a group that already possess the skills to undertake a prediction modelling study, have a strong working knowledge of how to apply their CPM to new datasets, and have a vested interest in any system that enables widespread evaluation and potential for implementation of the CPM. We include a brief outline of the four steps required to register a new CPM with the system in the Appendix.

For proprietary models, however, commercial incentives may present a more fundamental barrier: manufacturers have little motivation to facilitate rigorous external validation beyond what regulators require, and may seek approval with minimal evidence. In such cases, wider adoption may depend on regulators mandating more comprehensive and transparent ev-

idence of model performance. We therefore highlight two key stakeholder groups beyond the academic modelling community. For proprietary model developers, registration with the system offers a demonstrable commitment to transparency and independent scrutiny – functioning as a recognised marker of good practice that may help maintain the trust of clients and the public, and facilitate post- or pre-market surveillance of deployed tools. For regulators, a well-adopted registry could serve as a mechanism for requiring or incentivising independent external validation as a condition of market approval, or developers could use participation as evidence of their commitment to fully independent validation in support of regulatory submissions.

It is also likely that there may be resistance to change from established research practices toward our proposed system. Especially for regression models, not reporting coefficient estimates or association measures derived from them is a departure from current practice. We argue that this departure can be justified, as regression coefficients in a prediction model typically do not have straightforward interpretations (e.g. due to applied shrinkage, incomplete adjustment for confounders), and reporting them may not be crucial where other means of model evaluation are available. One alternative to publishing regression coefficients is to employ model-agnostic tools to explain the contribution of predictors to predictions that are considered acceptable for black-box models, such as SHAP values [31, 32].

7. Conclusion

7.1 A new paradigm

Clinical prediction models are failing to progress through the pipeline to actual implementation, evaluation in-situ, and impact on patient outcomes. A new paradigm is needed to bridge the gap between scientific rigour and the realities of

navigating the governance of CPMs in health-care. The two-component system proposed here offers one solution where researchers can evaluate CPMs safely and easily in any new setting, whilst maintaining data sovereignty. Developers are able to share their CPMs to calculate predictions as intended, without losing commercial viability. Ultimately the system will lead to more independent evaluation studies, covering a greater number of settings and populations, safeguarding the health service by increasing the evidence base for any CPM eventually adopted. Increasing the number of evaluation studies has been widely called for, and we hope this system will aid this call [3, 5, 24, 33]. We note that while this system was born out of the realities of funding a CPM’s implementation process, should situations arise where commercialisation is not necessary, developers can easily make the CPM specification open access using this system (i.e. using public rather than private repositories).

7.2 Call to action

We invite developers to register their CPMs in this system for use with the **evaluatr** package. We also encourage journals to recognise the use of the **evaluatr** system for reporting CPM development studies in their publication standards. To facilitate this in practice we recommend developers provide either an example of how the CPM can be evaluated using the system, or synthetic data to allow reviewers and editors the opportunity to test that the CPM can be accessed for evaluation purposes through this system [34]. The **evaluatr** package is available through GitHub (<https://github.com/JoieEnsor/evaluatr>) and we encourage community engagement through testing and suggesting refinements.

7.3 Final thoughts

Finally, clinical prediction modelling stands at an inflection point with current approaches lim-

iting translation to practice. Currently established practice and guidelines must evolve to match the realities of the modern healthcare and governance landscape. The choice between scientific integrity and clinical impact is a false dichotomy – this system and the **evaluatr** package offer one path to achieve both.

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Appendix

One-time setup: four steps to make a model available for independent evaluation <small>Requires a GitHub account and a working R model object/published specification - no additional infrastructure</small>	
1	<p>Create a private repository ~5 min</p> <p>Create a private GitHub repository to host the model specification. No special configuration is required beyond setting visibility to private. The repository can hold multiple model versions, each in its own subfolder – the folder name becomes the <code>model_id</code> that evaluators reference.</p> <p>File path convention: <code>models/<model_id>/specification.json</code></p>
2	<p>Generate the model specification file ~15 min</p> <p>Use the <code>generate_model_json()</code> utility function to produce a protected specification file directly from the R model object.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Supported CPM types: logistic, Cox, Weibull, and multinomial regression; extensible to other types ▪ Coefficient values are embedded in a protected format; they are not exposed to evaluators at any point ▪ Custom pre-processing code strings can be embedded for CPMs requiring data manipulation <p style="background-color: #ffe0b2; padding: 2px; border-radius: 5px; display: inline-block;">Coefficients never readable on file</p>
3	<p>Upload to the repository ~5 min</p> <p>Upload the generated specification file to the repository following the required folder structure. No further configuration is required – the <code>evaluator</code> package locates the file automatically using the repository address and model ID supplied to the evaluator.</p>
4	<p>Vet the evaluator and issue an access token ~5 min per evaluator</p> <p>For each evaluator, generate a fine-grained GitHub access token granting read-only access to the repository. Control and responsibility for vetting evaluators rests with the developer prior to issuing a token.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Verify institutional affiliation and absence of commercial conflict of interest ▪ Request a formal evaluation protocol – any legitimate evaluator should be able to provide one ▪ Issue a unique token per evaluator to permit selective revocation without affecting others ▪ Set a short expiration on the token – this limits the window of potential misuse <p style="background-color: #d9e1f2; padding: 2px; border-radius: 5px; display: inline-block;">Developer retains full control</p> Audit trail per evaluator
<p><i>Initial setup takes approximately 30 minutes for a first model. Subsequent models require only Steps 2–4. Step 4 is repeated for each evaluator granted access and takes approximately five minutes.</i></p>	

Box 2. The developer-side setup: four steps to make a model available for independent evaluation.